

CONFLICT MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES, LEADERSHIP DEVELOPMENT PRACTICES, AND THEIR SCHOOLS ORGANIZATION CULTURE AND CLIMATE

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to evaluate the levels of Conflict Management Strategies, Leadership Development Practices, and Organizational Culture and Climate among School Heads in Public Elementary Schools within the Division of Bohol during the 2023-2024 school year. It also explored potential relationships between leadership development practices and the identified variables, including conflict management strategies, organizational culture, and climate. A quantitative descriptive correlational design was employed using a survey method. The survey instrument was pilot-tested and validated by experts from the Department of Education to ensure reliability and validity. The study was conducted across 40 districts in CD1, CD2, and CD3, involving 660 respondents (110 school heads and 550 teachers) from Public Elementary Schools in the Bohol Division, using both Google forms and hard copies. Mean scores were used to assess the levels of organizational climate, culture, conflict management strategies, and leadership development, while standard deviation measured the variability of responses. Spearman's rank correlation was applied to analyze relationships between variables. Findings showed that both school heads and teachers demonstrated high proficiency in conflict resolution, feedback, and collaborative problem-solving. Leadership development practices were marked by strong dedication to skill development, succession planning, and leadership effectiveness. Participants exhibited alignment with organizational values, adherence to norms, and openness to new cultural elements. High levels of employee satisfaction, effective communication, and motivation were observed in the organizational climate. The study revealed significant positive relationships between leadership development practices and conflict management strategies, organizational culture, and climate. Effective leadership development was shown to positively impact these areas, improving employee satisfaction, engagement, and organizational cohesion. Proficient conflict management, supported by effective leadership, fostered healthier work

environments and stronger employee relationships. Based on these findings, school heads are encouraged to prioritize continuous professional development and program evaluation, while teachers should focus on enhancing their conflict management and communication skills. Continuous leadership learning is essential for optimizing organizational performance and effectiveness.

Keywords: *Conflict Management, Leadership Development, Organizational Climate, Organizational Culture, and Professional Development*

INTRODUCTION

School administrators bear the dual responsibility of managing both academic and administrative functions while also providing visionary leadership, fostering a positive school culture, and effectively resolving conflicts (Chandolia & Anastasiou, 2020). However, research has highlighted several challenges that complicate this role, particularly regarding the organizational climate and its impact on leadership development in schools (Bhaduri, 2019). The significance of this study lies in its attempt to explore these challenges, specifically in the context of schools in Bohol, a region that faces unique difficulties due to limited resources, geographical disparities, and the socio-economic diversity of its student population.

Despite the government's well-designed plans for improving education, obstacles frequently arise during implementation, especially at the school leadership level. Studies examining the perspectives of those directly affected by these policies—teachers, students, and parents—have demonstrated that statutory policies are often difficult to put into practice due to various challenges (Parojenog & Pabalan, 2024). For school administrators in Bohol, these challenges are further compounded by limited resources and the region's cultural context.

Research has shown that factors such as staff morale, communication breakdowns, and low levels of trust among educators are prevalent challenges in schools (Nabors, 2019). To address these, democratic leadership, along with ongoing professional development programs, has been proposed as an effective strategy. Yet, these programs are often insufficient, particularly in regions like Bohol, where educators and administrators still lack the necessary experience to ensure that student performance meets government standards.

The organizational culture of educational institutions in Bohol is heavily influenced by the region's historical and cultural context, which, in turn, affects the behaviors, attitudes, and values of educators and administrators. This study seeks to examine how these cultural practices impact leadership development, school climate, and conflict management strategies. The research is motivated by an acknowledgment of the complex challenges that Bohol's educational institutions face, particularly regarding the leadership capabilities of school administrators, the handling of conflicts, and the promotion of leadership growth.

Conflicts within schools, worsened by the COVID-19 pandemic, have highlighted the need for school leaders to enhance their conflict resolution skills (Kim & Park, 2020). Without adequate training and resources, many administrators struggle to manage conflicts effectively, resulting in a decline in trust and hindering leadership development efforts (Metwally et al., 2019). Furthermore, the pandemic exacerbated these issues, adding to the stress and uncertainty experienced by educators, students, and parents (Abdullah & Anwar, 2021). Addressing these challenges is essential for fostering an environment conducive to leadership development.

This study draws upon Transformational Leadership Theory, which emphasizes the role of visionary leadership in inspiring and motivating followers toward shared goals and personal growth (Asbari, 2020). The research will investigate how transformational leadership practices influence leadership development in Bohol's schools, as well as how conflict management strategies, organizational culture, and climate interact to shape leadership outcomes.

A gap exists in the current literature regarding the specific contextual factors in Bohol that influence leadership development. By focusing on the unique cultural, social, and economic conditions of the region, this study aims to provide insights into how these factors shape the effectiveness of leadership development programs. This research is expected to contribute to a better understanding of how to address the challenges faced by school administrators in Bohol, ultimately enhancing leadership capacities and improving the overall educational experience.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the conflict management strategies of school heads, leadership development practices, and the organizational culture and climate of Elementary schools in the Division of Bohol for the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the level of conflict management strategies practiced by school heads in terms of:
 - 1.1 conflict resolution;
 - 1.2 employee feedback; and,
 - 1.3 collaborative problem solving?
2. What is the level of leadership development practiced in terms of:
 - 2.1 leadership training and programs;
 - 2.2 succession planning; and,
 - 2.3 leadership effectiveness assessment?
3. What is the level of organizational culture in terms of:
 - 3.1 cultural alignment;
 - 3.2 employee behavior consistency; and,
 - 3.3 cultural adaptability?
4. What is the level of organizational climate in terms of:
 - 4.1 employee satisfaction;
 - 4.2 communication effectiveness; and,
 - 4.3 employee motivation?

5. Is there a significant relationship between leadership development practices and the identified variables:
 - 5.1 conflict management strategies
 - 5.2 organizational culture
 - 5.3 organizational climate
6. What action plan be proposed based on the result of the study as to enhance the leadership development practices of the school heads?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study sought to understand the School Heads' Conflict Management Strategies and Leadership Development Practices within selected institutions in Bohol. It employed a quantitative descriptive research design. Quantitative research aimed to elucidate, predict, and manage phenomena by examining the relationships between measurable variables. This referred to the quantitative analysis of phenomena and their interconnections.

Research Environment and Participants

The study was conducted in public elementary schools in the Division of Bohol. Bohol is located in the central portion of the Visayas, lying between Cebu to the northwest and Leyte to the northeast. The province has one city and is subdivided into 47 towns. It is composed of three congressional districts (CD1, CD2, and CD3). The illustration below presented the map of Bohol, specifying the three congressional districts as the study's locale.

The study included 110 randomly selected public elementary schools across the three Congressional Districts of Bohol, covering both medium and large schools. A total of 110 elementary school heads and 550 elementary teachers participated. The researcher used purposive random sampling, which allowed for the selection of participants who were most relevant to the study.

Distribution of Respondents

Name of Congressional Districts	School Heads	Teachers
CD 1	27	137
CD 2	41	204
CD 3	42	209
Total	110	550

Research Instrument

To arrive at the findings, the researcher used a modified survey questionnaire based on the studies of Gregory (2011), Akpan (2001), Aslanargun (2015), and Kalkan

et al. (2020). Pilot testing was conducted to ensure clarity and relevance. The survey had four parts: conflict management strategies (conflict resolution, employee feedback, problem-solving), leadership development practices (training, succession planning, effectiveness), organizational culture (alignment, behavior consistency, adaptability), and organizational climate (satisfaction, communication, motivation).

A four-point scale was used to rate the variables, with 4 being the highest ("Highly Practiced" or "Very Satisfied") and 1 the lowest ("Never Practiced" or "Not Satisfied"). This ensured a clear assessment of each aspect under study.

		Verbal Interpretation (per variable)		
Scale	Range	Level of Conflict Management Strategies Practice		
4	3.25 – 4.00	A- Always	HP- Highly Practiced	
3	2.50 – 3.24	SO-Sometimes	MP-Moderately Practiced	
2	1.75 – 2.49	S-Seldom	LP- Less Practiced	
1	1.00 – 1.74	N- Never	NP- Never Practiced	
		Verbal Interpretation (per variable)		
Scale	Range	Level of Leadership Development Practices		
4	3.25 – 4.00	A- Always	HP- Highly Practiced	
3	2.50 – 3.24	SO-Sometimes	MP-Moderately Practiced	
2	1.75 – 2.49	S-Seldom	LP- Less Practiced	
1	1.00 – 1.74	N- Never	NP- Never Practiced	
		Verbal Interpretation (per variable)		
		Level of Organizational Culture		
Scale	Range	Cultural Alignment	Employee Behavior Consistency	Cultural Adaptability
4	3.25 – 4.00	VWA – Very Well Aligned	VC-Very Consistent	VA- Very Adaptable
3	2.50 – 3.24	WA- Well Aligned	C- Consistent	Adaptable
2	1.75 – 2.49	LA- Less Aligned	LC- Less Consistent	LA- Less Adaptable
1	1.00 – 1.74	NA-Not Aligned	NC- Not Consistent	NA- Not Adaptable
		Verbal Interpretation (per variable)		
		Level of Organizational Climate		
Scale	Range	Employee Satisfaction	Communication Effectiveness	Employee Motivation
4	3.25 – 4.00	VS- Very Satisfied	VE – Very Effective	VM - Very Motivated
3	2.50 – 3.24	S- Satisfied	E– Effective	M – Motivated

2	1.75 – 2.49	LS- Less Satisfied	LE – Less Effective	LM- Less Motivated
1	1.00 – 1.74	NS – Not Satisfied	NE – Not Effective	NM- Not Motivated

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher followed the procedure of securing approval from the Dean of the School of Advanced Studies and obtained an official permit from the Schools Division Superintendent in the province of Bohol to conduct the study. Permission was also requested from the supervisors, teachers, and school heads of the selected schools in the area.

The researcher created online survey questionnaires using the Google Forms application and reached the respondents through their social media accounts, via email and Facebook Messenger. To ensure the validity of the instruments, the respondents were asked to answer the questionnaires honestly and were assured of the anonymity and confidentiality of their responses. They were given ample time to complete the survey.

Additionally, the researcher retrieved all the questionnaires on the same day they were administered to ensure that the data collection process was as efficient as possible.

Data Analysis

In the analysis of the data, the following procedures were followed. The responses were collected, tallied, and tabulated.

The mean score was used to determine the levels of conflict management strategies of school heads, leadership development practices, organizational culture and climate of the selected institutions.

The standard deviation was applied to tell how measurements for a group are spread out from the average (mean), or expected value among indicators.

On the other hand, the Spearman's rank correlation was employed to determine the significant relationship between variables.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the results obtained from the collected data on the levels of Conflict Management Strategies, Leadership Development Practices, and the Organizational Culture and Climate of Public Elementary School Heads and Teachers in the Division of Bohol for the School Year 2023-2024.

The tallied and collated data are presented in tabular form, analyzed using statistical formulas, and interpreted in relation to the research questions posed by this study.

Table 1.1
Conflict Management Strategies in Conflict Resolution

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Identifies and communicate conflicts early	3.61	HP	3.22	MP	3.42	HP	4
2. Provides of clear guidelines on resolving colleagues	3.67	HP	3.28	HP	3.48	HP	1.5
3. Addresses promptly to prevent escalation	3.64	HP	3.18	MP	3.41	HP	5
4. Encourages open dialogue to resolve disputes	3.67	HP	3.28	HP	3.48	HP	1.5
5. Clear channels for reporting conflicts	3.64	HP	3.24	MP	3.44	HP	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.65	Highly Practiced	3.24	Moderately Practiced	3.44	Highly Practiced	

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Interpretation (DI)	Weighted Mean Score (WMS)
4	3.25 – 4.00	HP- Highly Practiced	
3	2.50 – 3.24	MP- Moderately Practiced	
2	1.75 – 2.49	LP- Less Practiced	
1	1.00 – 1.74	NP- Never Practiced	

Table 1.1 presents Conflict Management Strategies in Conflict Resolution. School heads rate "identifying and communicating conflicts early" as "Highly Practiced" (WMS 3.61), while teachers rate it as "Moderately Practiced" (WMS 3.22), resulting in an overall score of 3.42. Both groups rate "providing clear guidelines" as "Highly Practiced" (WMS 3.67 for school heads, 3.28 for teachers).

For "addressing conflicts promptly," school heads rate it highly (WMS 3.64), but teachers rate it moderately (WMS 3.18), showing room for improvement in timely conflict resolution. "Encouraging open dialogue" is highly rated by both groups (WMS 3.67 for school heads, 3.28 for teachers), emphasizing communication and collaboration.

"Clear channels for reporting conflicts" is rated highly by school heads (WMS 3.64) but moderately by teachers (WMS 3.24), pointing to a need for better clarity in conflict reporting.

Overall, conflict resolution strategies are strong, but discrepancies between school heads and teachers highlight areas for improvement in timeliness and communication.

Table 1.2
Conflict Management Strategies in Employee Feedback

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Fosters a culture of continuous improvement	3.58	HP	3.19	MP	3.39	HP	4.5
2. Establishes regular forums to discuss employee feedback	3.68	HP	3.23	MP	3.46	HP	2
3. Gauges employee satisfaction with conflict resolution outcomes	3.59	HP	3.19	MP	3.39	HP	4.5
4. Encourages open communication, ensuring that employees feel heard and valued in the conflict resolution process	3.75	HP	3.28	HP	3.52	HP	1
5. Facilitates ongoing dialogue and improvement in conflict management	3.64	HP	3.26	HP	3.45	HP	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.65	Highly Practiced	3.23	Moderately Practiced	3.44	Highly Practiced	

Table 1.2 presents the Conflict Management Strategies in Employee Feedback. School heads rated "fostering a culture of continuous improvement" as "Highly Practiced" (WMS 3.58), while teachers rated it as "Moderately Practiced" (WMS 3.19), resulting in an overall score of 3.39, indicating a need for better alignment.

For "establishing regular forums for employee feedback," school heads rated it "Highly Practiced" (WMS 3.68), and teachers rated it "Moderately Practiced" (WMS 3.23), leading to an overall score of 3.46, emphasizing the importance of regular feedback.

Both groups rated "gauging employee satisfaction with conflict resolution" as "Highly Practiced" overall (WMS 3.59 for school heads, 3.19 for teachers), with a total score of 3.39, showing commitment to employee satisfaction.

"Encouraging open communication" was rated "Highly Practiced" by both school heads (WMS 3.75) and teachers (WMS 3.28), reflecting the organization's dedication to communication. Similarly, "facilitating ongoing dialogue" was rated "Highly Practiced" by both groups (WMS 3.64 for school heads and 3.26 for teachers), showing strong commitment to improvement.

Overall, the organization emphasizes open communication and collaboration, but differences between school heads and teachers suggest the need for better alignment.

Table 1.3
Conflict Management Strategies in Collaborative Problem Solving

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Emphasizes teamwork and collective decision-making	3.79	HP	3.36	HP	3.58	HP	1
2. Encourages to brainstorm and contributes to problem-solving	3.77	HP	3.29	HP	3.53	HP	2
3. Fosters a culture of shared responsibility	3.77	HP	3.20	MP	3.49	HP	3.5
4. Initiates training and professional development	3.71	HP	3.23	MP	3.47	HP	5
5. Provides resources and tools to support collaborative problem-solving among staff members	3.73	HP	3.24	HP	3.49	HP	3.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.75	Highly Practiced	3.26	Highly Practiced	3.51	Highly Practiced	

Table 1.3 highlights Conflict Management Strategies in Collaborative Problem Solving. Both school heads and teachers rated "teamwork and collective decision-making" as "Highly Practiced" (WMS 3.79 for school heads, 3.36 for teachers), with an overall score of 3.58, showing strong collaboration efforts.

For "brainstorming and problem-solving," both groups rated it "Highly Practiced" (WMS 3.77 for school heads, 3.29 for teachers), with an overall score of 3.53, reflecting a culture of innovation.

"Fostering shared responsibility" was rated highly by school heads (WMS 3.77) but moderately by teachers (WMS 3.20), resulting in a score of 3.49, suggesting a need for more teacher involvement.

"Training and development" were rated highly by school heads (WMS 3.71) and moderately by teachers (WMS 3.23), leading to a score of 3.47, indicating a proactive approach to staff development with room for improvement.

Lastly, "providing resources for problem-solving" was rated highly by both groups (WMS 3.73 for school heads, 3.24 for teachers), with a score of 3.49, showing commitment to equipping staff for collaboration.

Overall, the organization demonstrates strong collaborative practices, with opportunities to increase teacher engagement in shared responsibility and development.

Table 2.1

Leadership Development Practice in Leadership Training and Program

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Offers leadership training & development programs	3.50	HP	3.26	HP	3.38	HP	3
2. Provides a variety of leadership training opportunities	3.49	HP	3.17	MP	3.33	HP	4
3. Establishes feedback loops	3.46	HP	3.16	MP	3.31	HP	5
4. Participates in leadership training programs	3.65	HP	3.27	HP	3.46	HP	1
5. Establishes evaluation metrics	3.53	HP	3.29	HP	3.41	HP	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.53	Highly Practiced	3.23	Moderately Practiced	3.38	Highly Practiced	

Table 2.1 summarizes Leadership Development Practices in Leadership Training and Programs. Both school heads and teachers rated "offering leadership training" as "Highly Practiced" (WMS 3.50 for school heads, 3.26 for teachers), showing strong commitment to leadership development.

For "providing a variety of training opportunities," school heads rated it highly (WMS 3.49), but teachers rated it moderately (WMS 3.17), suggesting a need for more accessible options for teachers.

"Establishing feedback loops" was rated highly by school heads (WMS 3.46) but moderately by teachers (WMS 3.16), with an overall score of 3.31, indicating room for better feedback mechanisms.

Both groups rated "participation in leadership training" as highly practiced (WMS 3.65 for school heads, 3.27 for teachers), with an overall score of 3.46, showing strong engagement.

"Establishing evaluation metrics" was also rated highly (WMS 3.53 for school heads, 3.29 for teachers), emphasizing the importance of clear assessments.

Overall, leadership development is strong, but improvements are needed in training accessibility and feedback systems.

Table 2.2
Leadership Development Practice in Succession Planning

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Engages in mentoring and coaching programs	3.51	HP	3.30	HP	3.41	HP	1.5
2. Identifies and nurtures emerging leaders	3.57	HP	3.25	HP	3.41	HP	1.5
3. Communicates succession planning efforts	3.46	HP	3.21	MP	3.34	HP	5
4. Aligns with the long-term strategic goals of the institution	3.47	HP	3.25	HP	3.36	HP	4
5. Invests in the development of high-potential employees for future leadership roles	3.56	HP	3.20	MP	3.38	HP	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.51	Highly Practiced	3.24	Highly Practiced	3.38	Highly Practiced	

Table 2.2 highlights Leadership Development Practices in Succession Planning. Both school heads and teachers actively engage in mentoring and coaching (WMS 3.51 for school heads, 3.30 for teachers), emphasizing leadership growth.

"Identifying and nurturing emerging leaders" is also "Highly Practiced" (WMS 3.57 for school heads, 3.25 for teachers), reflecting a strategic approach to developing future leaders.

However, "communicating succession planning" is rated highly by school heads (WMS 3.46) but moderately by teachers (WMS 3.21), indicating a need for clearer communication.

Both groups rate "aligning with strategic goals" as "Highly Practiced" (WMS 3.47 for school heads, 3.25 for teachers), showing strong alignment with the institution's mission.

"Investing in high-potential employees" is rated highly by school heads (WMS 3.56) but moderately by teachers (WMS 3.20), highlighting a need for better resource access.

Overall, succession planning is effective, but improvements in communication and resource access are needed.

Table 2.3
Leadership Development Practice in Leadership Effectiveness Assessment

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Conducts programs regularly within our organization	3.56	HP	3.24	MP	3.40	HP	3.5
2. Involves multi-source feedback	3.56	HP	3.24	MP	3.40	HP	3.5
3. Utilizes performance metrics and key performance indicators	3.54	HP	3.31	HP	3.43	HP	2
4. Establishes continuous feedback mechanisms	3.55	HP	3.23	MP	3.39	HP	5
5. Informs professional development plans for school heads	3.64	HP	3.28	HP	3.46	HP	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.57	Highly Practiced	3.26	Highly Practiced	3.42	Highly Practiced	

Table 2.3 presents Leadership Development Practices in Leadership Effectiveness Assessment. Both "conducting programs regularly" and "involving multi-source feedback" are rated "Highly Practiced" overall (WMS 3.56), but teachers view them as "Moderately Practiced" (WMS 3.24), while school heads rate them "Highly Practiced" (WMS 3.56), suggesting a gap in communication or implementation.

"Utilizing performance metrics and key performance indicators" is rated "Highly Practiced" by both school heads (WMS 3.54) and teachers (WMS 3.31), indicating effective use of assessment tools.

"Establishing continuous feedback mechanisms" is highly practiced overall (WMS 3.55), though teachers rate it as "Moderately Practiced" (WMS 3.23), showing a similar perception gap.

"Informing professional development plans for school heads" is rated "Highly Practiced" overall (WMS 3.64), reflecting strong implementation of professional development initiatives.

Overall, leadership effectiveness assessments are conducted regularly, with a focus on continuous improvement, multi-source feedback, and the use of performance metrics. Tailoring professional development based on assessments further supports leadership growth and improvement.

**Table 3.1
Organizational Culture in Cultural Alignment**

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Clarity in communicating values	3.45	VWA	3.27	VWA	3.36	VWA	3.5
2. Emphasis of mission and vision throughout the organization as a shared sense of purpose	3.45	VWA	3.30	VWA	3.38	VWA	2
3. Connection between individual goals and the organization's overarching objectives	3.45	VWA	3.27	VWA	3.36	VWA	3.5
4. Exercising of daily practices and decision-making based on established cultural norms and values	3.54	VWA	3.30	VWA	3.42	VWA	1
5. Reinforcement of desired organizational culture in all interactions and initiative	3.46	VWA	3.23	WA	3.35	VWA	5
Average Weighted Mean	3.47	Very Well Aligned	3.27	Very Well Aligned	3.37	Very Well Aligned	

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Interpretation (DI)	Weighted Mean Score (WMS)
4	3.25 – 4.00	VWA- Very Well Aligned	
3	2.50 – 3.24	WA- Well Aligned	
2	1.75 – 2.49	LA- Less Aligned	
1	1.00 – 1.74	NA- Never Aligned	

Table 3.1 highlights Cultural Alignment within Organizational Culture. Both school heads and teachers perceive clarity in communicating values as "Very Well Aligned" (VWA), with weighted mean scores (WMS) of 3.45 for school heads and 3.27 for teachers, indicating strong communication of core values.

For "emphasizing mission and vision as a shared purpose," both groups rate it as "Very Well Aligned" (WMS: 3.45 for school heads, 3.30 for teachers), reflecting a strong alignment with the organization's purpose.

In "daily practices and decision-making based on cultural norms and values," both school heads and teachers rate it as "Very Well Aligned" (WMS: 3.54 for school heads, 3.30 for teachers), indicating effective integration of cultural values into operations.

However, for "reinforcing desired culture in all interactions," while school heads rate it "Very Well Aligned" (WMS: 3.46), teachers rate it "Moderately Aligned" (WMS: 3.23), suggesting a need for improvement in consistent cultural reinforcement.

Overall, the organization's culture is well-aligned with its values and objectives, though slight differences in perception among teachers suggest areas for targeted improvement.

Table 3.2
Organizational Culture in Employee Behavior Consistency

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Adherence to organizational norms	3.48	VC	3.25	VC	3.66	VC	1
2. Exhibiting uniform behavior in handling challenges and conflicts, reflecting organizational values	3.47	VC	3.29	VC	3.38	VC	5
3. Application of organizational policies	3.49	VC	3.29	VC	3.39	VC	4
4. Exercise of professional conduct	3.59	VC	3.34	VC	3.47	VC	2
5. Demonstration of collaborative and cooperative approach of team members	3.56	VC	3.27	VC	3.42	VC	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.52	Very Consistent	3.29	Very Consistent	3.46	Very Consistent	

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Interpretation (DI)	Weighted Mean Score (WMS)
4	3.25 – 4.00	VC- Very Consistent	
3	2.50 – 3.24	C- Consistent	
2	1.75 – 2.49	LC- Less Consistent	
1	1.00 – 1.74	NC- Never Consistent	

Table 3.2 highlights Organizational Culture in Employee Behavior Consistency. Both school heads and teachers rated "adherence to organizational norms" as "Very Consistent" (WMS 3.48 for school heads, 3.25 for teachers), indicating strong alignment with norms.

"Exhibiting uniform behavior in handling challenges" was also rated "Very Consistent" (WMS 3.47 for school heads, 3.29 for teachers), reflecting alignment with organizational values.

The "application of organizational policies" received similar ratings (WMS 3.49 for school heads, 3.29 for teachers), showing consistent policy adherence.

"Professional conduct" was rated highly consistent by both groups (WMS 3.59 for school heads, 3.34 for teachers), as was "collaborative teamwork" (WMS 3.56 for school heads, 3.27 for teachers).

Overall, both groups demonstrate consistent adherence to norms, policies, professionalism, and collaboration, fostering a cohesive organizational culture.

Table 3.3
Organizational Culture in Cultural Adaptability

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Cultural practices to evolving business needs	3.41	VA	3.19	A	3.30	VA	5
2. Willingness to embrace new cultural elements introduced within the organization	3.48	VA	3.29	VA	3.39	VA	3
3. Flexibility and openness to diverse perspectives	3.44	VA	3.31	VA	3.38	VA	4
4. Training and development initiatives	3.50	VA	3.33	VA	3.42	VA	1
5. Feedbacking from employees to identify areas for cultural improvement and adaptation	3.47	VA	3.32	VA	3.40	VA	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.46	Very Adaptable	3.29	Very Adaptable	3.38	Very Adaptable	

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Interpretation (DI)	Weighted Mean Score (WMS)
4	3.25 – 4.00	VA- Very Adaptable	
3	2.50 – 3.24	A- Adaptable	
2	1.75 – 2.49	LA- Less Adaptable	
1	1.00 – 1.74	NA- Never Adaptable	

Table 3.3 evaluates Organizational Culture in Cultural Adaptability. Both school heads and teachers' rate "cultural practices to evolving business needs" as "Very Adaptable" (WMS 3.41 for school heads, 3.19 for teachers), with an overall score of 3.30, indicating room for improvement in aligning cultural practices with evolving needs.

"Embracing new cultural elements" also received high ratings (WMS 3.48 for school heads, 3.29 for teachers), reflecting a commitment to fostering innovation. Similarly, "flexibility and openness to diverse perspectives" is rated positively, with a "Very Adaptable" rating (WMS 3.44 for school heads, 3.31 for teachers).

Both groups emphasize the importance of "training and development" to support adaptability (WMS 3.50 for school heads, 3.33 for teachers), along with the role of "employee feedback" in driving cultural improvement (WMS 3.47 for school heads, 3.32 for teachers).

Overall, the organization demonstrates strong adaptability, openness to change, and commitment to continuous learning, but could further improve in aligning cultural practices with evolving needs.

**Table 4.1
Organization Climate in Employee Satisfaction**

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Quality of working environment in our institution	3.65	VS	3.35	VS	3.50	VS	2.5
2. Recognition of contributions to the success of the organization	3.70	VS	3.30	VS	3.50	VS	2.5
3. Provision of opportunities for employee growth and development	3.68	VS	3.30	VS	3.49	VS	4
4. Addressing employees' concerns	3.68	VS	3.28	VS	3.68	VS	1
5. Attention to well-being of its employee	3.67	VS	3.25	VS	3.48	VS	5
Average Weighted Mean	3.68	Very Satisfied	3.31	Very Satisfied	3.53	Very Satisfied	

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Interpretation (DI)	Weighted Mean Score (WMS)
4	3.25 – 4.00	VS- Very Satisfied	
3	2.50 – 3.24	S- Satisfied	
2	1.75 – 2.49	LS- Less Satisfied	
1	1.00 – 1.74	NS- Never Satisfied	

Table 4.1 highlights Organizational Climate in Employee Satisfaction. Both school heads and teachers rated the "quality of the working environment" highly, with a "Very Satisfied" (VS) interpretation (WMS 3.65 for school heads, 3.35 for teachers), indicating positive perceptions of the workplace.

The "recognition of contributions" was also rated as "Very Satisfied" by both groups (WMS 3.70 for school heads, 3.30 for teachers), emphasizing the value placed on employee recognition.

“Opportunities for growth and development” received similarly high satisfaction ratings (WMS 3.68 for school heads, 3.30 for teachers), indicating that employees feel supported in their advancement.

Both groups rated “addressing employee concerns” as “Very Satisfied” (WMS 3.68 for school heads, 3.28 for teachers), reflecting the organization's responsiveness to concerns.

Lastly, “attention to employee well-being” was highly rated by both school heads and teachers (WMS 3.67 for school heads, 3.25 for teachers), showing a strong commitment to employee welfare.

Overall, employees expressed high satisfaction with the working environment, recognition, growth opportunities, concern resolution, and well-being support, suggesting a positive organizational climate. Addressing any minor differences in perception between groups can further enhance this satisfaction.

Table 4.2
Organization Climate in Communication Effectiveness

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Communication within our institution is widely observed	3.62	VE	3.28	VE	3.45	VE	1
2. Quality of Information flow	3.55	VE	3.23	E	3.39	VE	4
3. Openness and inclusivity communication culture	3.66	VE	3.21	E	3.44	VE	2.5
4. Communication of organization's vision	3.63	VE	3.25	VE	3.44	VE	2.5
5. Timeliness dissemination of critical updates and changes across the organization	3.49	VE	3.15	E	3.32	VE	5
Average Weighted Mean	3.59	Very Effective	3.22	Effective	3.41	Very Effective	

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Interpretation (DI)	Weighted Mean Score (WMS)
4	3.25 – 4.00	VE- Very Effective	
3	2.50 – 3.24	E- Effective	
2	1.75 – 2.49	LE- Less Effective	
1	1.00 – 1.74	NE- Never Effective	

Table 4.2 shows positive perceptions of communication effectiveness within the institution. Both school heads and teachers rated "communication within the institution" highly (WMS 3.62 for school heads, 3.28 for teachers), indicating "Very Effective" practices.

The "quality of information flow" was rated slightly lower by teachers (WMS 3.55 for school heads, 3.23 for teachers), but still classified as "Effective." This suggests a need for improvement in seamless information flow.

"Openness and inclusivity in communication" was rated "Very Effective" by school heads (WMS 3.66) and "Effective" by teachers (WMS 3.21), showing room for better inclusivity.

"Communication of the organization's vision" was rated "Very Effective" by both groups, reflecting strong alignment with the institution's goals.

Finally, the "timeliness of critical updates" was rated highly by school heads (WMS 3.49) but slightly lower by teachers (WMS 3.15), emphasizing the need for timely communication.

Overall, communication is effective, but areas like inclusivity and timeliness could be improved to ensure consistent satisfaction across the organization.

**Table 4.3
Organization Climate in Employee Motivation**

Statement	School Heads n=110		Teachers n=550		Overall		
	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	WMS	DI	Rank
1. Recognition and rewards for outstanding performance	3.65	VM	3.25	VM	3.45	VM	1
2. Provision of opportunities for skill development and career growth	3.60	VM	3.28	VM	3.44	VM	2
3. Valuing employee input in decision-making processes	3.57	VM	3.23	M	3.40	VM	4.5
4. Alignment of work assignments with individual strengths and interests	3.63	VM	3.17	M	3.40	VM	4.5
5. Team-building activities and initiatives	3.55	VM	3.31	VM	3.43	VM	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.60	Very Motivated	3.25	Very Motivated	3.42	Very Motivated	

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Interpretation (DI)	Weighted Mean Score (WMS)
4	3.25 – 4.00	VM- Very Motivated	
3	2.50 – 3.24	M- Motivated	
2	1.75 – 2.49	LM- Motivated	
1	1.00 – 1.74	NM- Motivated	

Table 4.3 highlights Organization Climate in Employee Motivation. Both school heads and teachers highly value "recognition and rewards for outstanding performance," with a WMS of 3.65 for school heads and 3.25 for teachers, categorizing it as "Very Motivated" (VM), emphasizing the importance of acknowledging contributions.

"Opportunities for skill development and career growth" are also highly valued, with WMS of 3.60 for school heads and 3.28 for teachers, underscoring the importance of professional growth for motivation.

"Valuing employee input in decision-making" received positive ratings (WMS 3.57 for school heads, 3.23 for teachers), highlighting the need for employee involvement.

"Aligning work assignments with strengths" was rated highly (WMS 3.63 for school heads, 3.17 for teachers), showing the impact of aligning tasks with employee strengths on motivation.

"Team-building activities" were similarly valued (WMS 3.55 for school heads, 3.31 for teachers), emphasizing the role of team cohesion.

Overall, the institution strongly supports employee motivation through recognition, development opportunities, involvement in decisions, task alignment, and team-building activities.

Table 5.1
Relationship between Leadership Development Practices and Conflict Management Strategies

Variables	Spearman's rho	Sig. (2-tailed)	N	Decision	Interpretation
Leadership Development Practices and Conflict Management Strategies	.830**	.000	660	Reject Ho	Significant; Ho; Rejected; Related

*Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 5.1 shows a strong positive correlation between leadership development practices and conflict management strategies, with a Spearman's rho of 0.830, significant at the 0.01 level. This suggests that organizations with robust leadership development programs are better at managing conflicts effectively. Strong leadership fosters open communication, trust, and collaboration, key factors in resolving conflicts.

Rahim (2023) supports this, highlighting the role of leadership in conflict management and the need for leadership development to improve conflict resolution skills. This correlation emphasizes that effective leadership development enhances conflict resolution within organizations.

Table 5.2
Relationship between Leadership Development Practices and Organizational Culture

Variables	Spearman's rho	Sig. (2-tailed)	N	Decision	Interpretation
Leadership Development Practices and Organizational Culture	.705**	.000	660	Reject H ₀	Significant; H ₀ ; Rejected; Related

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)*

Table 5.2 shows a strong positive correlation between leadership development practices and organizational culture, with a Spearman's rho of 0.705, significant at the 0.01 level. This suggests that effective leadership development is closely linked to a positive organizational culture. Strong leadership practices help shape and reinforce shared values, norms, and behaviors within the organization.

Xenikou (2022) supports this by explaining how leadership behaviors influence organizational culture and employee performance, emphasizing the importance of leadership development in cultivating a strong organizational culture.

Table 5.3
Relationship between Leadership Development Practices and Organizational Climate

Variables	Spearman's rho	Sig. (2-tailed)	N	Decision	Interpretation
Leadership Development Practice and Organizational Climate	.695**	.000	660	Reject H ₀	Significant; H ₀ ; Rejected; Related

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)*

Table 5.3 shows a strong positive correlation between leadership development practices and organizational climate, with a Spearman's rho of 0.695, significant at the 0.01 level. This indicates that effective leadership development is closely tied to a positive organizational climate, including employee satisfaction and engagement.

Avolio and Hannah (2008) highlight that transformational leadership, supported by structured development programs, creates a supportive work environment.

DISCUSSION

Findings

The analysis looked at different aspects of organizations, from how employees feel about their work environment to how well they communicate and handle conflicts.

1.1 Level of Conflict Management Strategies Practiced by School Heads as to Conflict Resolution. In conflict management strategies for conflict resolution, both school heads and teachers exhibit a proactive approach. With an average weighted mean score (WMS) of 3.65 for school heads and 3.24 for teachers, indicating 'Highly Practiced' and 'Moderately Practiced' respectively, it demonstrates a strong commitment to effective conflict resolution strategies within the institution.

1.2 Level of Conflict Management Strategies Practiced by School Heads as to Employee Feedback. In implementing conflict management strategies concerning employee feedback, both school heads and teachers exhibit a strong commitment to fostering a culture of continuous improvement. With average weighted mean scores (WMS) of 3.65 indicating 'Highly Practiced' and 3.23 as 'Moderately Practiced', respectively, they underscore the institution's dedication to effective conflict resolution strategies.

1.3 Level of Conflict Management Strategies Practiced by School Heads as to Collaborative Problem Solving. In collaborative problem-solving strategies, both school heads and teachers demonstrate a strong commitment to fostering teamwork and collective decision-making, as indicated by their highly practiced average weighted mean scores (WMS) of 3.75 and 3.26, respectively, classified as 'Highly Practiced'.

2.1. Level of Leadership Development Practice as to Leadership Training and Programs. In leadership development practices, both school heads and teachers demonstrate a strong commitment to fostering leadership skills and growth opportunities, with school heads achieving a 'Highly Practiced' average weighted mean score (WMS) of 3.53 and teachers achieving a 'Moderately Practiced score of 3.23'.

2.2 Level of Leadership Development Practice as to Succession Planning. In succession planning within leadership development practices, both school heads and teachers show a proactive stance, with school heads achieving a 'Highly Practiced' average weighted mean score (WMS) of 3.51 and teachers achieving a 'Moderately Practiced' score of 3.24.

2.3 Level of Leadership Development Practice as to Leadership Effectiveness Assessment. In assessing leadership effectiveness within leadership development practices, both school heads and teachers demonstrate a commitment to continuous improvement, as evidenced by their high average weighted mean scores (WMS) of 3.57 and 3.26, both classified as 'Highly Practiced', respectively.

3.1 Level of Organizational Culture as to Cultural Alignment. The evaluation of cultural alignment within the organization indicates a strong sense of alignment among both school heads and teachers, with a WMS of 3.47 for school heads and 3.27 for teachers, signifying 'Very Well-Aligned' values.

3.2 Level of Organizational Culture Employee Behavior Consistency. The analysis shows a strong adherence to organizational norms and policies among both school heads and teachers, with an average weighted mean score (WMS) of 3.52 for school heads and 3.29 for teachers, indicating 'Very Consistent' values.

3.3 Level of Organizational Culture as to Cultural Adaptability. The assessment reveals a willingness to embrace new cultural elements among both school heads and teachers, with average weighted mean scores (WMS) of 3.46 for school heads and 3.29 for teachers, indicating practices are "Very Adaptable." This underscores openness to diverse perspectives and initiatives for training and development to meet evolving business needs.

4.1 Level of Organizational Climate as to Employee Satisfaction. The analysis of organizational climate for employee satisfaction shows a consistently high level of satisfaction among school heads, with an overall weighted mean score (WMS) of 3.68, reflecting a 'Very Satisfied' sentiment. Teachers also express high satisfaction, albeit slightly lower, with an average WMS of 3.31 as 'Very Satisfied'

4.2 Level of Organizational Climate as to Communication Effectiveness. Communication within the organization is highly effective for both school heads and teachers, with a weighted mean score (WMS) of 3.59 for school heads and 3.22 for teachers, indicating that it is 'Highly Effective' and 'Moderately Effective' respectively.

4.3 Level of Organizational Climate as to Employee Motivation. Both school heads and teachers demonstrate high motivation, with weighted mean scores (WMS) of 3.60 and 3.25, respectively, indicating a 'Very Motivated' sentiment.

5.1 Significant Relationship Between Leadership Development Practices and Conflict Management Strategies. The relationship between leadership development practices and conflict management strategies is highly significant, with a Spearman's rho correlation coefficient of .830** ($p < .01$).

5.2 Significant Relationship Between Leadership Development Practices and Organizational Culture. The relationship between leadership development practices and organizational culture is significantly positive, as indicated by a Spearman's rho correlation coefficient of .705** ($p < .01$).

5.3 Significant Relationship Between Leadership Development Practices and Organizational Climate. The relationship between leadership development practices and organizational climate is found to be significantly positive, with a Spearman's rho correlation coefficient of .695** ($p < .01$).

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the researcher concludes that the institution demonstrates a strong commitment to conflict management, leadership development, and fostering a positive organizational culture and climate. School heads and teachers actively engage in conflict resolution, employee feedback, and collaborative problem-solving, with school heads consistently rating these practices as more highly implemented than teachers. Leadership development practices, including training, succession planning, and effectiveness assessments, are robust but show room for improvement in teacher involvement.

The organizational culture is well-aligned, with consistent employee behavior and adaptability to new cultural elements. Both school heads and teachers report high levels of satisfaction, communication effectiveness, and motivation, although teachers tend to rate these aspects slightly lower.

Furthermore, there is a significant positive relationship between leadership development practices and conflict management, organizational culture, and organizational climate. This highlights the importance of leadership development in creating a productive, cohesive, and adaptive work environment. Continued focus on leadership initiatives will enhance conflict resolution, employee engagement, and overall organizational success.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Increase Teacher Participation in Leadership Development Programs.** Encourage greater teacher involvement in leadership training, succession planning, and effectiveness assessments to ensure balanced development and inclusion across all staff.
2. **Enhance Communication and Conflict Resolution Practices.** Improve transparency, timeliness, and consistency in communication and conflict management strategies, addressing the gaps perceived by teachers.
3. **Promote and Support Cultural Adaptability.** Continue to embrace new cultural elements and offer additional training and development opportunities to help staff adapt to evolving institutional and business needs.
4. **Boost Employee Motivation and Satisfaction.** Implement more personalized recognition and reward programs, along with targeted professional development opportunities, to address slight gaps in teacher motivation and satisfaction.
5. **Strengthen Feedback Loops and Decision-Making Involvement.** Foster open communication and ensure that employee feedback is consistently gathered and acted upon, creating an environment of continuous improvement and engagement.
6. **Invest in Leadership Development to Enhance Organizational Climate.** Continue focusing on leadership initiatives that reinforce a positive organizational climate and culture, ensuring a cohesive and motivated workforce.

By adopting these recommendations, the institution can further enhance its leadership practices, organizational culture, and overall work environment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Informed consent was acquired by the researcher. The participants were informed that they may leave the study at any time. The respondents' anonymity was preserved and their well-being was protected. The study's conduct was free from any conflicts of interest. Plagiarism was avoided. The results were utilized exclusively for research. And there was no bias in the interpretation of the data.

PROPOSED ACTION PLAN TO ENHANCE THE LEADERSHIP DEVELOPMENT PRACTICES OF THE SCHOOL HEADS

Rationale

Effective leadership within educational institutions is fundamental to achieving academic excellence, fostering a positive school culture, and promoting professional growth among educators. By enhancing leadership development practices for school heads, the institution can address various challenges and capitalize on opportunities to create a thriving learning environment. The rationale for this action plan is rooted in several key factors.

In addition, strong leadership has a direct impact on organizational performance and student outcomes. Effective school leaders can inspire and empower teachers, leading to improved student engagement, achievement, and overall school success. Secondly, leadership development initiatives promote a culture of collaboration and shared responsibility among school leaders. By providing opportunities for networking, peer learning, and mentorship, school heads can exchange ideas, share best practices, and collectively address challenges facing the institution.

Through investing in leadership development enhances job satisfaction and career advancement opportunities for school leaders, contributing to higher levels of staff retention and attracting top talent to leadership positions.

This ensures continuity and stability within the organization while also aligning closely with the institution's mission, vision, and values. By prioritizing leadership development, the school demonstrates its commitment to fostering ethical leadership, promoting diversity and inclusion, and creating a supportive and inclusive work environment for all stakeholders.

Objectives

This proposed action plan aims to provide information on the importance of leadership skills, and management skills of school heads. In addition, this will improve leadership skills and competencies among school heads, foster a culture of collaboration,

innovation, and continuous improvement, and enhance organizational effectiveness and promote a positive school climate.

Mechanics of Implementation

A copy of the proposed training program will be submitted with the approved permit to conduct a face-to-face training program for approval of the in-charge in Training and Development Unit and Schools Division Superintendent.

Schedule of the Implementation

The following are the schedule of implementation:

Leadership training programs

Quarterly sessions starting from Q2 of the fiscal year.

Mentorship and coaching programs

Ongoing throughout the year, with monthly coaching sessions.

Peer learning communities

Bi-monthly meetings starting from Q3 of the fiscal year.

Leadership retreats and workshops

Annual retreat in Q4 of the fiscal year, with additional workshops scheduled as needed.

Monitoring and Evaluation System

The program implementers will conduct pre- and post-training assessments to measure changes in leadership competencies. Administer participant feedback surveys after each training session, coaching session, and event. Track attendance and participation in peer learning communities and leadership events. Review progress against established performance indicators quarterly and make adjustments as needed.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, N. N., & Anwar, G. (2021). Global Financial Outlook during the COVID-19 Pandemic: The role of effective leadership styles on Financial outlook. Available at SSRN 3824670.
- Akpan, C. P. (2001). Motivating Teachers for effective job performance: A note to school administrators. *West African Journal of Research and Development in Education (WAJRAD)*, 8(1).
- Asbari, M. (2020). Is transformational leadership suitable for future organizational needs?. *International Journal of Social, Policy and Law*, 1(1), 51-55.
- Aslanargun, E. (2015). Teachers' expectations and school administration: Keys of better communication in schools. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 15(60), 17-34.
- Avolio, B. J., & Hannah, S. T. (2008). Developmental readiness: Accelerating leader development. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 60(4), 331–347.
- Bhaduri, R. M. (2019). Leveraging culture and leadership in crisis

- management. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 43(5/6), 554-569.
- Chandolia, E., & Anastasiou, S. (2020). Leadership and conflict management style are associated with the effectiveness of school conflict management in the Region of Epirus, NW Greece. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, 10(1), 455-468.
- Gregory, K. (2011). The importance of employee satisfaction. *The Journal of the Division of Business & Information Management*, 5, 29-37.
- Kalkan, Ü., Altınay Aksal, F., Altınay Gazi, Z., Atasoy, R., & Dağlı, G. (2020). The relationship between school administrators' leadership styles, school culture, and organizational image. *Sage Open*, 10(1), 2158244020902081.
- Kim, E. J., & Park, S. (2020). Transformational leadership, knowledge sharing, organizational climate and learning: an empirical study. *Leadership & organization development journal*, 41(6), 761-775.
- Metwally, D., Ruiz-Palomino, P., Metwally, M., & Gartzia, L. (2019). How ethical leadership shapes employees' readiness to change: The mediating role of an organizational culture of effectiveness. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 2493.
- Nabors, B. R. (2019). A correlational study of organizational trust, manager transparency, and employee stress (Doctoral dissertation, University of Phoenix).
- Parojenog, R., & Pabalan, A. P. (2024). Enhancing Basic Education Standards: A Framework for Quality Advancement. Available at SSRN 4801978.
- Rahim, M. A. (2023). *Managing conflict in organizations*. Routledge.
- Xenikou, A. (2022). Leadership and organizational culture. In *Handbook of research methods for Organisational culture* (pp. 23-38). Edward Elgar Publishing.